

1 Article

2 Influence of bone level dental implants placement and cortical 3 thickness on osseointegration: *In silico* and *in vivo* studies.

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Abstract: The aim of this study was to evaluate the biomechanical behavior of bone level dental implants with three different placement: bone level, 0.5 mm above and below bone level. In addition, the influence of thickness cortical bone on osseointegration has been determined due to the mechanical loads transfer from the dental implant to cortical and trabecular bone. The thickness studied were 1.5 mm and 2.5 mm. Numerical simulations were performed using a Finite Element Method (FEM) based-model. In order to verify the FEM model, the *in silico* results were compared with the results obtained from histological analysis performed in an in-vivo study with New Zealand rabbits. FEM was performed using a computerized 3D model of Bone Level dental implants inserted in the lower jaw bone with an applied axial load of 100 N. The analysis was performed using the different distances from the bone level and different thickness of cortical bone. Interface area of bone growth was evaluated by analyzing the Bone-Implant-Contact (BIC), Region of interest (ROI) and Total Bone Area (BAT) parameters obtained from in-vivo histological process and analyzed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Bone Level implants were inserted in the rabbit tibia, placing two implants per tibia. These parameters were evaluated after three and six weeks of implantation. FEM studies showed that the placement 0.5 mm below the bone level presented lower values of stress distribution compared to the other studied placement. The lower levels of mechanical stress were then correlated with the in vivo studies, showing that this position presented the highest BIC value after 3 and 6 weeks of implantation. In this placement it can be observed bone growth in vertical up the bone level. The thinner thickness of the study shows a better transfer of mechanical loads and this leads to a better osseointegration in the thinner one. *In silico* and *in vivo* results both concluded that the implants placed 0.5 mm below the cortical bone and with lower thickness presented the best biomechanical and histological behavior in terms of new bone formation, enhanced mechanical stability and optimum osseointegration.

Keywords: Bone Level, dental implants, titanium, FEM, finite elements method, osseointegration, cortical bone, in vivo, implant neck design, histology.

46 **1. Introduction**

47 Bone behavior when dental implants are placed at the osseous level has different
48 factors that will affect their growth or loss. These factors are: macro and micro implant
49 design [1-4], separation between placed implants [5], periodontal and bone quality [6],
50 occlusal loading [7] and the microgap prone to bacteria colonization in the implant
51 abutment connection and in consequence the location of this connection in relation to
52 the bone crest [8-12]. Some studies show peri-implant bone losses of between 1-2 mm
53 after the first year of occlusal loading, and of 0.1 to 0.2 mm over successive years [13-15].
54 However, Pellicer et al. observed as the different placement of the bone level implant
55 could produce bone growth with different behavior in a analysis of different clinical
56 studies [16].

57 Placement of an implant in a deeper position with respect to the bone crest
58 (subcrestal placement) has been suggested as a method that could contribute to maintain
59 the periimplant soft and hard tissues in comparison with crestal placement, though this
60 affirmation is subject to controversy. As early as 1969, Branemark [17] recommended
61 placing the implant below the bone crest to prevent implant exposure during bone
62 remodeling.

63 Different studies [18-20] have demonstrated that bone level dental implants placed
64 approximately 2 mm below the bone crest are associated with significantly less
65 peri-implant bone loss compared to implants placed at crestal level. However, other
66 researchers [20-25] have observed greater bone loss with implants placed at subcrestal
67 level. This bone loss has been explained by the peri-implantitis [26] and it is necessary
68 the elimination of biofilm from the dental implants [27-30]. In relation to the bone
69 growth, the placement of an implant in a subcrestal position has been suggested as a
70 method that could contribute to the maintenance of hard and soft periimplant tissues
71 compared to a crestal placement – though this affirmation is subject to debate.
72 Experimental animal studies [21,25, 31-32] and human studies [20, 33-35] have observed
73 that subcrestal implant placement produces an increase in peri-implant bone loss.

74 Esposito et al. [36] and Sanz et al. [37] published two meta-analyses that compared
75 efficacy of implant placement with immediate or delayed implant placement. Both
76 studies concluded that more clinical studies are required to establish clear conclusions
77 and clinical guidelines regarding the timing of implant placement. Subsequently, there
78 has been a considerable increase in the number of clinical studies investigating the
79 efficacy of early implant placement. However, there is no systematic review to provide
80 quantitative and qualitative overview of the recently available evidence on this topic.
81 Hence, there is a need to carry out a study using the finite element method to study the
82 load transfer in the different subcrestal, crestal and upcrestal situations. Load transfer is
83 a key factor in bone formation and bone loss [38-40]. This finite element modelling will
84 be validated on implant rabbit implants in all three positions. In addition, an important
85 factor for load transfer for the same implant design is the thickness of the bone crest. The
86 stress levels in the bone will give us the possible bone formation that will be validated
87 by the histologies performed. Although bone formation and loss has multiple factors, as
88 described above, this paper aims to clarify the role of occlusal loading.

89 **2. Materials and Methods**

90 *2.1. Finite Element Analysis methodology*

91 A 3D finite element based-model was created to simulate the osseointegrated
92 implant in the posterior mandible, allowing representing cortical and trabecular bone
93 (Figure 1). The dental implant studied was a bone level dental implant (Vega, Klockner
94 dental implant system, Escaldes Engordany, Andorra). A universal, adaptive and
95 user-friendly pre and post processor for numerical simulations, called GiD29, was used
96 to create the FEM model and to generate the 3D finite element meshes. The model
97 consisted of a trabecular bone, surrounded by a 5mm-thick cortical bone layer. The
98 dimensions of the bone-implant model were 35 mm in height. A 5 mm thick bone was

modeled around the implant. All combined, the model presented a total height of 45 mm, 10mm in bucco-lingual width and 10 mm in mesio-distal length. The titanium implant was modeled as 40 mm in length with a 4.5 mm diameter (Figure 2). The implant-bone system is herein proposed for the first time, being the version model 1.0. Materials were considered linear and isotropic, having an elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio show in Table 1 [41-42]. Details on the FEM model can be found in previous references [43-44].

Figure 1. Implant model and finite element mesh. XXX Elements and ZZZ nodes.

The geometry of the whole model is displayed in figure 2:

Figure 2. The whole model: implant, cortical one and trabecular bone.

Both cortical and trabecular bone has been considered as elastic and isotropic materials. The mechanical properties of the materials are listed below:

Table 1. Mechanical properties of all the model's materials.

Material	Young's modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio
Implant	110,000	0.34
Cortical bone	17,000	0.30
Trabecular bone	56	0.28

The proposed model was meshed with 4-noded tetrahedral like elements, with a mesh size of 0.2 mm for implants and 3 mm for bone components, streamlined by means of a threaded model. In order to analyze the behavior in the different points of the neck, different points were initially analyzed in order to determine the number of nodes and elements. Once the mesh sensitivity analysis was performed, all components were meshed, obtaining the number of elements and nodes required for the study.

132 In order to perform the mechanical analysis, the proposed system (Dental implant,
133 Cortical bone and Trabecular bone) was embedded in its three directions. Movement
134 was restricted on the sides and on the lower areas, mimicking the real scenario of dental
135 implant placement into bone (Figure 2). The COMET software 34 was used to perform
136 the FEM analysis. The software allowed visualizing the meshes and the obtained results
137 during calculation, such as Von Mises tension and its distribution along the proposed
138 model. In this analysis, the model was considered isotropic and homogeneous,
139 presenting perfect contact interface. A 100 N compression axial force was applied to
140 simulate the average forces generated by the mastication process.

141 2.2. *In vivo animal implantation*

142 For the *in vivo* animal study, twelve adult New Zealand rabbits were selected as
143 animal model. The surgeries were performed according to the protocol approved for this
144 study by the Faculty of Veterinary Sciences of the University of Cordoba (Spain) under
145 the registration number P01/0144. Osseointegration implant behavior was studied after 3
146 and 6 weeks of implantation. After 6 weeks of implantation, it is generally accepted that
147 it is possible to observe consolidated bone tissue, which is necessary to validate the
148 results obtained in the numerical analysis. Two samples were implanted in each
149 proximal metaphysis of the animal tibiae, resulting in 28 samples for the first
150 implantation period and 20 implants for the second implantation period. Samples were
151 randomly distributed in the different animals.

152 After the proposed time points, animals were sacrificed and samples were
153 harvested from each animal. Undecalcified samples were then immediately fixed in 10%
154 formaldehyde solution for 3 weeks to preserve tissue structure.

155 In order to reduce the size of the harvested tissues and samples, these were cut with
156 a diamond saw (Exakt 310, Exakt, Germany). The cut sections were then immersed in a
157 formaldehyde solution for 48h to assure bone tissue fixation, followed by dehydration
158 by immersion in ethanol solutions. After complete dehydration, samples were
159 embedded in methyl methacrylate resin Technovit (Kulzer-Heraeus, Germany). In order
160 to enhance resin penetration, resin concentration was progressively increased with time
161 together with constant stirring at 50 rpm under vacuum conditions. The resin embedded
162 tissues were finally photo-polymerized in a light control unit (Histolux, Kulzer-Heraeus,
163 Germany) with an external water cooling system. Samples were exposed to white light
164 and to UV light to obtain a solid transparent block to allow cutting.

165 Once the polymerized resin block was obtained, it was cut into 4 mm thick slices
166 with a diamond saw (Exakt 310, Exakt, Germany). Samples were then polished using a
167 grinding machine (Exakt 400CS, Exakt, Germany) with abrasive papers until a flat
168 surface was obtained for proper visualization. Finally, polished samples were then
169 carbon coated for SEM examination.

170 Polished samples were individually observed using Surface Scanning Electron
171 Focused Ion Beam (Zeiss, Germany) equipment with backscattered electrons detector to
172 observe undecalcified bone. Observation was performed at a charging potential of 15kV
173 with an 8mm working distance to achieve a resolution of up to 1.1 nm. The different
174 SEM images were merged by image analysis program ImageJ (NIH, USA) to create a
175 single high resolution image. The final images were then used to quantify
176 Bone-Implant-Contact (BIC) parameter, which relates the percentage of mineralized
177 bone in intimate contact with surface material implant. BIC parameter was evaluated at
178 20 magnification from implant perimeter all along neck length for all analyzed samples.
179 In addition, from the histologies has been calculated the bone ingrowth into the threads
180 (BAT) and the bone density 1mm outside the implant threads (ROI). More than 1,000
181 samples were analyzed with the optical microscope

182 In order to determine significant differences between the experimental groups, the
183 data was analyzed with single factor ANOVA and the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis
184 test using a statistical software Minitab ® 16 (Minitab Inc., USA) with 95% as confidence
185 interval.

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3. Results and Discussion.

The described model has been analyzed using the Finite Element Method (FE) in the three positions (cases) described:

- Case A: 0.5 mm above the bone surface ($h=+0.5$)
- Case B: at the same level of the bone surface ($h=0$)
- Case C: 0.5 mm below the bone surface ($h=-0.5$)

Since the stability of the implant can vary according to the cortical-bone thickness, the three cases mentioned above have been analyzed for two different thickness of the cortical bone:

- $t=1.5$ mm (cortical thickness)
- $t=2.5$ mm (cortical thickness)

The results of the FE analyses in all the models are reported below.

Figure 3 displays the Von Mises stresses when the implant modeled at the position $h=0$, it means the implant is located at the same level of the bone surface. Stresses in cortical bone are much larger in cortical bone (over 230 MPa) than in trabecular bone (7 MPa). In cortical bone the stresses shown a maximum value at the implant surface. However, in trabecular bone the stresses are maximum in a region close to the head of the implant and they decrease progressively with bone depth. When the thickness of the cortical bone decreases the stresses on both the cortical and the trabecular bone increase.

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Figure 3. Von Mises stresses. Left column: cortical bone. Right column: trabecular bone. Top row: cortical thickness 2.5 mm. Bottom row: cortical thickness 1.5 mm.

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Figure 4 shows the strains computed when the implant modeled at the position $h=0$. Unlike the stresses distribution, the strains are greater in trabecular bone (over 2.5%) than in the cortical bone where strains are below the 0.6% regardless the cortical bone thickness. In trabecular bone larger strains are observed in the region close to the cortical bone and around the top surface of the implant. As the cortical bone thickness decreases the strains in both cortical and trabecular bone increase.

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Figure 4. Strains. Top: cortical thickness 2.5 mm. Bottom: cortical thickness 1.5 mm.

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The figure 5 displays both stresses and strains with a cortical-bone thickness of 2.5 mm for the three cases studied herein. It can be observed that as the implant penetrates further into the jaw, the stresses on the cortical bone (left column of figure) decrease by around 100 to 50 MPa. Regarding the strains (right column of figure) the changes in the cortical bone strains are negligible but in the trabecular bone, the region where the strain exceeds 2.5% increases as the implantation depth increases.

246
 247 **Figure 5.** Von Mises stresses and strains with a cortical-bone thickness of 2.5 mm. Left column:
 248 stresses at cortical bone. Center column: stresses at trabecular bone. Right column: strains. Top
 249 row: Case A ($h=+0.5$). Middle row: Case B ($h=0$). Bottom row: Case C ($h=-0.5$).

250 The figure 6 shows similar results as in figure 6 but now the cortical-bone thickness
 251 is smaller (1.5 mm).

Figure 6. Von Mises stresses and strains with a cortical-bone thickness of 1.5 mm. Left column: stresses at cortical bone. Center column: stresses at trabecular bone. Right column: strains. Top row: Case A ($h=+0.5$). Middle row: Case B ($h=0$). Bottom row: Case C ($h=-0.5$).

Similar to the case of the thicker cortical bone, it can be seen that as the implant penetrates further into the jaw, the stresses on the cortical bone (left column of figure) decrease while stresses at trabecular bone (center column of figure) increase. However, unlike the case of thicker cortical bone, both the stresses in cortical and trabecular bone are greater and the difference when the implant is buried further in the bone is more evident. The maximum stresses in the cortical bone decrease by around 230 to 160 MPa, while in the trabecular bone, the area where the stresses are greater than 7 MPa increases up to 3 threads of the implant thread. Changes in the strains of the cortical bone in the case of a thinner cortical bone are still negligible (right column figures), but in the trabecular bone, the region where the strain exceeds 2.5% is sensitive to the implant position.

Figures 7, 8 and 9 show some histologies of the bone level dental implants for those placed 0.5 mm above the bone, at the same level as the bone and 0.5 mm below the bone level at the different implantation times: 3 and 6 weeks and for the different bone thicknesses 1.5 and 2.5 mm respectively.

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Figure 7. Histologies of the different bone level dental implant inserted 0.5 mm above of bone level. ($h=+0.5\text{mm}$). A. 3 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 1.5 mm. B. 6 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 1.5 mm. C. 3 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 2.5 mm. D. 6 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 2.5 mm.

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Figure 8. Histologies of the different bone level dental implant inserted at bone level. ($h=0\text{mm}$). A. 3 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 1.5 mm. B. 6 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 1.5 mm. C. 3 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 2.5 mm. D. 6 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 2.5 mm.

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Figure 9. Histologies of the different bone level dental implant inserted at 0.5 below the bone level. ($h=-0.5\text{mm}$). A. 3 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 1.5 mm. B. 6 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 1.5 mm. C. 3 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 2.5 mm. D. 6 weeks implanted and bone thickness of 2.5 mm.

The high sensitivity image analysis studies performed in the scanning electron microscope for each dental implant allowed us to obtain the results of bone growth: BIC, BAT and ROI, which indicate the osseointegration capacity of the dental implants under the different conditions studied. The results are shown in Table 2 for those implanted in bone with a cortex thickness of 1.5 mm and in Table 3 for a cortex thickness of 2.5 mm.

Table 2. Bone index contact (BIC), Total Bone area (BAT) and region of interest bone growth (ROI) for different types of Ti dental implant surfaces and after 3 and 6 weeks of implantation. Cortical thickness of 1.5 mm. Statistical differences for each column are indicated by single-asterisk ($P < 0.05$).

Thickness: 1.5mm

BIC	3 weeks	6 weeks
Above 0.5 mm	22% ± 5%	27% ± 8%
Bone level	29% ± 6%	33 % ± 9%
Below 0.5 mm	35% ± 6%*	55% ± 8%*
BAT	3 weeks	6 weeks
Above 0.5 mm	26% ± 4%	32% ± 7%
Bone level	32% ± 9%	40% ± 8%
Below 0.5 mm	40% ± 6%*	62% ± 5%*
ROI	3 weeks	6 weeks
Above 0.5 mm	18 ± 7%	25% ± 6%
Bone level	24% ± 6%	38% ± 8%
Below 0.5 mm	30% ± 5%*	55% ± 7%*

Table 3. Bone index contact (BIC), Total Bone area (BAT) and region of interest bone growth (ROI) for different types of Ti dental implant surfaces and after 3 and 6 weeks of implantation. Cortical thickness of 1.5 mm. Statistical differences for each column are indicated by single-asterisk ($P < 0.05$).

Thickness: 2.5mm

BIC	3 weeks	6 weeks
Above 0.5 mm	12% ± 3%	19% ± 5%
Bone level	18% ± 6%	25 % ± 9%
Below 0.5 mm	29% ± 4%*	39% ± 9%*
BAT	3 weeks	6 weeks
Above 0.5 mm	16% ± 4%	27% ± 8%
Bone level	26% ± 6%	35% ± 9%
Below 0.5 mm	35% ± 5%*	48% ± 5%*
ROI	3 weeks	6 weeks
Above 0.5 mm	20 ± 5%	26% ± 4%
Bone level	25% ± 6%	32% ± 5%
Below 0.5 mm	29% ± 8%*	45% ± 8%*

In all cases, with statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$), osseointegration levels (BIC, BAT and ROI) are greater at implantation times of 6 weeks than at 3 weeks, as expected.

The results for the two cortical thicknesses studied show that dental implants implanted 0.5 mm below bone level give the highest levels of osseointegration compared to implants implanted at bone level and those implanted above bone level 0.5 mm. These differences were statistically significant.

These results validate the finite element model applied since we could observe that it was in this condition where the transfer of mechanical loads to the cancellous tissue

310 was greater. It should be borne in mind that load transfer in this type of bone tissue
311 favors the formation of new bone as cancellous tissue is much more vascularized than
312 cortical tissue. It can also be observed that dental implants placed at bone level have
313 better levels of osseointegration but with a non-statistically significant difference with
314 $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.13$). Dental implants placed above the bone level have the worst BIC, BAT
315 and ROI results as established by the load transfer results obtained by finite element
316 analysis.

317 From the results shown in Tables 2 and 3 it can also be affirmed that the thickness
318 of the cortical bone exerts an opposite effect on osseointegration, i.e. the thicker the
319 cortical bone, the lower the BIC, BAT and ROI values than the values obtained for
320 implants placed in cortical bones of lesser thickness. These results have been obtained in
321 different clinical studies but there was no clear interpretation of the reason for this. The
322 finite elements have helped us to see that load transfer when the thickness is 1.5 mm is
323 much more effective for bone growth than when the thickness is 2.5 mm, as in this case
324 much greater tension is absorbed and produces a significant decrease in the levels of
325 tension in the trabecular bone, which does not favour the formation of new bone. As we
326 have also commented previously, cancellous bone favours the formation of new bone
327 with mechanical stimulation due to the fact that it is more vascularised than compact
328 bone.

329 In this research it has been carried out with tapered bone level dental implants with
330 a certain neck design. It should be noted that although commercial dental implants are
331 very similar in shape for optimising mechanical transfer to the bone, the different
332 designs could modify some of the results of those studied in this work. This limitation
333 would not affect the thickness of the cortex, but there could be small differences with the
334 angles of conicity of the implant. It must be taken into account that the designs of the
335 implant necks cannot be very angulated, since it has been observed that the mechanical
336 stress on the cortical bone causes so much compressive load that the blood vessels
337 collapse, producing bone necrosis. That is why, in this type of dental implants, large
338 bone resorption occurs, causing empty areas of V-shaped bone that are susceptible to
339 bacterial colonization and the initiation of a peri-implantitis process

340 The results obtained *in silico* and validated *in vivo* are according to the
341 meta-analysis realized by Bassir et al. [46]. In this study, there was no statistically
342 significant difference in crestal bone changes between subcrestal and equicrestal implant
343 positioning; however, subcrestal position resulted in higher bone levels. Neither
344 mucosal recession nor vertical mucosa thickness was influenced by different implant
345 placement depths. A 5-year randomized clinical trial by de Siqueira et al. [47] showed
346 that subcrestal implant placement had less bone loss and resulted in no implant thread
347 exposure, whereas with equicrestal placement, thread exposure occurred in one implant
348 after 5-year follow-up. It is, therefore, speculated that a subcrestal implant placement of
349 at least 1 mm can prevent possible biological complications due to implant rough
350 surface exposure. Our results also are in agreement with previous studies that
351 demonstrated the subcrestal implants produce more bone tissue and minimize bone
352 resorption [48-55]. In addition, the clinical relevance of this result is that subcrestal
353 placement may reduce the risk of having peri-implantitis by minimizing rough surface
354 exposure [53, 56]. A similar finding was reported by Vervaeke and coworkers in a 2-year
355 follow-up study [57] and in a 3-year follow-up using platform-switched implants [48].
356

5. Conclusions

FEM simulation studies show that bone level dental implants placed subcrestal have a lower load transfer to bone than dental implants at bone level and above the bone crest. This occlusal load transfer favours bone formation, followed by equicrestal dental implants and the worst load transfer is for implants placed above the bone crest. It has also been determined that the thinner cortical bone favours adequate load transfer and that the more vascularised cancellous tissue favours bone growth. These *in silico* results are validated by *in vivo* studies, where bone growth (BIC, BAT and ROI) can be seen for subcrestal dental implants with bone growth that can exceed the level of the bone crest. The results of equicrestals and upper crestal implants were also validated. In addition, histologies showed that thinner thicknesses favour bone formation.

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Informed consent: For this type of study, formal consent is not required.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors reject any conflicts of interest.

References

1. Canullo L, Micarelli C, Lembo-Fazio L, Iannello G, Clementini M. Microscopical and microbiologic characterization of customized titanium abutments after different cleaning procedures. *Clin. Oral Impl. Res.* 2014; 25:328–36.
2. Gil J, Pérez R, Herrero-Climent M, Rizo-Gorrita M, Torres-Lagares D, Gutierrez JL. Benefits of residual aluminium oxide for sand blasting titanium dental implants: Osseointegration and bactericidal effects. *Materials* 2022, 15:178. <https://10.3390/ma15010178>
3. Herrero-Climent M, López-Jarana P, Lemos BF, Gil FJ, Falcao C, Rios-Santos JV, Rios-Carrasco B. Relevant design aspects to improve the stability of titanium dental implants. *Materials* 2020, 13: 1910 doi.10.3390/ma13081910.
4. Nicolas-Silvente AI, Velasco-Ortega E, Ortiz-García I, Monsalve-Guil L, Gil FJ, Jimenez-Guerra A. Influence of the Titanium implants surface treatment on the surface roughness and chemical composition. *Materials* 2020, 13: 314. Doi:10.3390/ma13020314.
5. Rodríguez-Ciurana X, Vela-Nebot X, Segalà-Torres M, Calvo-Guirado JL, Camba J, Méndez-Blando V. The effect of interimplant distance on the height of the interimplant bone crest when using platform-switched implants. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent.* 2009; 29:141–51.
6. Linkevicius T, Apse P, Grybauskas S, Puisys A. Th influence of soft tissue thickness on crestal bone changes around implants: a 1-year prospective controlled clinical trial. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 2009; 24:712–19.
7. Naert I, Duyck J, Vandamme K. Occlusal overload and bone/implant loss. *Clin. Oral Implants Res.* 2012; 23:95–107.
8. Prosper L, Redaelli S, Pasi M, Zarone F, Radaelli G, Gherlone EF. A randomized prospective multicenter trial evaluating the platform-switching technique for the prevention of postrestorative crestal bone loss. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 2009; 24:299–308.
9. Canullo L, Fedele GR, Iannello G, Jepsen S. Platform switching and marginal bone-level alterations: the results of a randomized-controlled trial. *Clinical Oral Implants Research.* 2010; 21:115–21.
10. Romanos GE. Wound healing in immediately loaded implants. *Periodontology* 2000. 2015; 68:153–67.
11. Hoyos M, Velasco F, Ginebra MP, Manero JM, Gil FJ, Mas-Moruno C. Regenerating bone via multifunctional coatings: the blending of cell integration and bacterial inhibition properties on the Surface of biomaterials. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces.* 2019, 11 (40): 36449–36457. DOI: 10.1021/acsami.
12. Hoyos-Nogués M, Buxadera-Palomero J, Ginebra MP, Manero JM, Gil FJ, Mas-Moruno C. All-in-one trifunctional strategy: a cell adhesive, bacteriostatic and bactericidal coating for titanium implants. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces.* 2018, 169:30–40. doi: 10.1016/j.colsurfb.2018.04.050
13. Albrektsson T, Zarb G, Worthington P, Eriksson AR. The long-term efficacy of currently used dental implants: a review and proposed criteria of success. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 1986; 1:11–25.

- 412 14. Roos-Jansaker AM, Lindahl C, Renvert H, Renvert S. Nine-to fourteen-year follow-up of implant treatment. Part II: presence
413 of peri-implant lesions. *J Clin Periodontol* 2006; 33:290–5.
- 414 15. Jemt T, Lekholm U. Single implants and buccal bone grafts in the anterior maxilla: measurements of buccal crestal contours in
415 a 6-year prospective clinical study. *Clin. Impl. Dent. Rel. Res.* 2005; 7:127–35.
- 416 16. Pellicer-Chover H, Díaz-Sánchez M, Soto-Peñaloza D, Peñarrocha-Diago MA, Canullo L, Peñarrocha-Oltra D. Impact of
417 crestal and subcrestal implant placement upon changes in marginal peri-implant bone level. A systematic review. *Med Oral*
418 *Patol Oral Cir Bucal.* 2019;24(5): 673-683. doi:10.4317/medoral.23006.
- 419 17. Brånemark PI, Adell R, Breine U, Hansson BO, Lindström J, Ohlsson A. Intra-osseous anchorage of dental prostheses. I.
420 Experimental studies. *Scand J Plast Reconstr Surg.* 1969; 3:81–100.
- 421 18. Hermann JS, Cochran DL, Nummikoski PV, Buser D. Crestal bone changes around titanium implants. A radiographic
422 evaluation of unloaded nonsubmerged and submerged implants in the canine mandible. *Journal of periodontology.* 1997;
423 68:1117–30.
- 424 19. Galindo-Moreno P, León-Cano A, Ortega-Oller I, Monje A, O'Valle F, Catena A. Marginal bone loss as success criterion in
425 implant dentistry: beyond 2 mm. *Clin Oral Impl Res.* 2015, 26:28-34.
- 426 20. Esposito M, Grusovin MG, Tzanetea E, Piattelli A, Worthington HV. Interventions for replacing missing teeth: treatment of
427 perimplantitis. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2010; 16:4970.
- 428 21. Hämmerle CH, Brägger U, Bürgin W, Lang NP. The effect of subcrestal placement of the polished surface of ITI implants on
429 marginal soft and hard tissues. *Clinical oral implants research.* 1996; 7:111–9.
- 430 22. Cesaretti G, Lang NP, Salata LA, Schweikert MT, Gutierrez Hernandez ME, Botticelli D. Sub-crestal positioning of implants
431 results in higher bony crest resorption: an experimental study in dogs. *Clin. Oral Impl Res.* 2015; 26:1355–60.
- 432 23. Stein AE, McGlmpy EA, Johnston WM, Larsen PE. Effects of implant design and surface roughness on crestal bone and soft
433 tissue levels in the esthetic zone. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 2009; 24:910–9.
- 434 24. Broggini N, McManus LM, Hermann JS, Medina RU, Oates TW, Schenk RK. Persistent acute inflammation at the
435 implant-abutment interface. *J Dent Res.* 2003; 82:232–7.
- 436 25. Piattelli A, Vrespa G, Petrone G, Iezzi G, Annibaldi S, Scarano A. Role of the Microgap Between Implant and Abutment: A
437 Retrospective Histologic Evaluation in Monkeys. *Journal of Periodontology.* 2003; 74:346–52.
- 438 26. Armitage GC, Xenoudi P. Post-treatment supportive care for the natural dentition and dental implants. *Periodontology*
439 2000. 2016; 71:164–84.
- 440 27. Punset, M.; Villarrasa, J.; Nart, J.; Manero, J.M.; Bosch, B.; Padrós, R.; Perez, R.A.; Gil, F.J. Citric Acid Passivation of Titanium
441 Dental Implants for Minimizing Bacterial Colonization Impact. *Coatings* 2021, 11, 214. [https://doi.org/10.3390/
442 coatings11020214](https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings11020214).
- 443 28. Godoy-Gallardo, M.; Wang, Z.; Shen, Y.; Manero, J. M.; Gil, F. J.; Rodríguez, D.; Haapasalo, M., Antibacterial coatings on
444 titanium surfaces: a comparison study between in vitro single-species and multispecies biofilm. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*
445 2015, 7 (10), 5992-6001.
- 446 29. Godoy-Gallardo, M.; Manzanares-Céspedes, M. C.; Sevilla, P.; Nart, J.; Manzanares, N.; Manero, J. M.; Gil, F. J.; Boyd, S. K.;
447 Rodríguez, D., Evaluation of bone loss in antibacterial coated dental implants: An experimental study in dogs. *Mater Sci Eng*
448 *C Mater Biol Appl* 2016, 69, 538-45.
- 449 30. Gil, F.J.; Rodríguez, A.; Espinar, E.; Llamas, J.M.; Padulles, E.; Juarez, A. Effect of the oral bacteria on the mechanical behavior
450 of titanium dental implants. *Int. J. Oral Maxillofac. Impl.* 2012, 27, 64–68.
- 451 31. Buser D, Weber HP, Lang NP. Tissue integration of non-submerged implants. 1-year results of a prospective study with 100
452 ITI hollow-cylinder and hollow-screw implants. *Clinical oral implants research.* 1990; 1:33–40.
- 453 32. Wennerberg A, Albrektsson T, Andersson B, Krol JJ. A histomorphometric and removal torque study of screw-shaped
454 titanium implants with three different surface topographies. *Clinical Oral Impl Res.* 1995; 6:24–30.
- 455 33. Degidi M, Perrotti V, Shibli JA, Novaes AB, Piattelli A, Iezzi G. Equicrestal and subcrestal dental implants: A histologic and
456 histomorphometric evaluation of nine retrieved human implants. *Journal of Periodontology.* 2011; 82:708–15.
- 457 34. Donovan R, Fetner A, Koutouzis T, Lundgren T. Crestal bone changes around implants with reduced abutment diameter
458 placed non-submerged and at subcrestal positions: a 1-year radiographic evaluation. *J Periodontol.* 2010; 81:428–34.
- 459 35. Aimetti M, Ferrarotti F, Mariani GM, Ghelardoni C, Romano F. Soft tissue and crestal bone changes around implants with
460 platform-switched abutments placed nonsubmerged at subcrestal position: a 2-year clinical and radiographic evaluation. *Int J*
461 *Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 2015; 30:1369–77.
- 462 36. Esposito M, Grusovin MG, Polyzos IP, Felice P, Worthington HV. Interventions for replacing missing teeth: dental implants in
463 fresh extraction sockets (immediate, immediate-delayed and delayed implants). *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2010: CD005968.
- 464 37. Sanz I, Garcia-Gargallo M, Herrera D, Martin C, Figuero E, Sanz M. Surgical protocols for early implant placement in
465 post-extraction sockets: a systematic review. *Clin Oral Implants Res.* 2012; 23(Suppl 5): 67– 79.
- 466 38. Albrektsson T, Wennerberg A. On osseointegration in relation to implant surfaces. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res.* 2019 Mar;21
467 Suppl 1:4-7. doi: 10.1111/cid.12742.
- 468 39. Javed F, Ahmed HB, Crespi R, Romanos GE. Role of primary stability for successful osseointegration of dental implants:
469 factors of influence and evaluation. *Interv Med Appl Sci* 2013; 5:162-7.
- 470 40. Meltzer AM. Primary stability and initial bone-to-implant contact: the effects on immediate placement and restoration of
471 dental implants. *J Implant Reconstruct Dent* 2009; 1:35-41.

- 472 41. Boyer R, Welsch G, Collings EW. *Materials Properties Handbook: Titanium Alloys*. ASM International; 1994.
473 <https://books.google.es/books?id=x3rToHWOCd8C&printsec=frontcover&hl=ca#v=onepage&q&f=false>. Accessed May 17,
474 2018.
- 475 42. Middleton J, Jones ML, Pande GN. *Computer Methods in Biomechanics & Biomedical Engineering--2*. Gordon and Breach
476 Science Publishers; 1998.
477 https://books.google.es/books?id=iLB2spvLxvIC&pg=PA698&lpg=PA698&dq=bone+elastic+modulus+13700&source=bl&ots=J8Ym9rJeFZ&sig=RGHKazVNL1LnO9moL7XK0O-4m-0&hl=ca&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwil4ufa5ozbAhUBlxQKHSnsB_cQ6AEwAHoECAEQLg#v=onepage&q=bone elastic modulus.
- 480 43. Zienkiewicz OC. *The Finite Element Method*. McGraw-Hill Ed. London; 1977.
- 481 44. Gallagher RH. *Finite Element Analysis: Fundamentals*. Prentice-Hall. New York; 1974.
- 482 45. Weblet Importer. <http://www.cimne.com/comet/>. Barcelona. Accessed May 17, 2018.
- 483 46. Bassir SH, El Kholy K, Chen ChY, Lee KH, Intini G. Outcome of early dental implant placement versus other dental implant
484 placement protocols: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Periodontol*. 2019, 90(5): 493-506.
- 485 47. de Siqueira RAC, Savaget Gonçalves Junior R, dos Santos PGF, de Mattias Sartori IA, Wang H-L, Fontão FNGK. Effect of
486 different implant placement depths on crestal bone levels and soft tissue behavior: A 5-year randomized clinical trial. *Clin
487 Oral Impl Res*. 2020; 31:282–293. <https://doi.org/10.1111/clar.13569>
- 488 48. Al Amri, M. D., Al-Johany, S. S., Al Baker, A. M., Al Rifaiy, M. Q., Abduljabbar, T. S., & Al-Kheraif, A. A. Soft tissue changes
489 and crestal bone loss around platform-switched implants placed at crestal and subcrestal levels: 36-month results from a
490 prospective split-mouth clinical trial. *Clinical Oral Implants Research*, 2017, 28(11), 1342 – 1347.
491 <https://doi.org/10.1111/clar.12990>.
- 492 49. Koh, R. U., Oh, T. J., Rudek, I., Neiva, G. F., Misch, C. E., Rothman, E. D., & Wang, H. L. Hard and soft tissue changes after
493 crestal and subcrestal immediate implant placement. *Journal of Periodontology*, 2011, 82(8), 1112 – 1120.
494 <https://doi.org/10.1902/jop.2011.100541>
- 495 50. Koutouzis, T., Neiva, R., Nair, M., Nonhoff, J., & Lundgren, T. Cone beam computed tomographic evaluation of implants with
496 platform-switched Morse taper connection with the implant-abutment interface at different levels in relation to the alveolar crest.
497 *International Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Implants*, 2014, 29(5), 1157– 1163. <https://doi.org/10.11607/jomi.3411>.
- 498 51. Palaska, I., Tsaousoglou, P., Vouros, I., Konstantinidis, A., Menexes, G. Influence of placement depth and abutment
499 connection pattern on bone remodeling around 1-stage implants: A prospective randomized controlled clinical trial. *Clinical
500 Oral Implants Research*, 2016; 27(2): 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/clar.12527>.
- 501 52. Barros, R. R., Novaes, A. B. Jr, Muglia, V. A., Iezzi, G., Piattelli, A. Influence of interimplant distances and placement depth on
502 peri-implant bone remodeling of adjacent and immediately loaded Morse cone connection implants: A histomorphometric study in
503 dogs. *Clinical Oral Implants Research*, 2010; 21(4), 371–378. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0501.2009.01860.x>.
- 504 53. Monje, A., Galindo-Moreno, P., Tozum, T. F., Suarez-Lopez del Amo, F., Wang, H. L. Into the paradigm of local factors as
505 contributors for peri-implant disease: Short communication. *International Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Implants*, 2016;
506 31(2), 288–292. <https://doi.org/10.11607/jomi.4265>
- 507 54. Novaes, A. B. Jr, Barros, R. R., Muglia, V. A., & Borges, G. J. Influence of interimplant distances and placement depth on
508 papilla
509 formation and crestal resorption: A clinical and radiographic study in dogs. *Journal of Oral Implantology*, 2009; 35(1), 18–27.
510 <https://doi.org/10.1563/1548-1336-35.1.18>
- 511 55. Novoa, L., Batalla, P., Caneiro, L., Pico, A., Linares, A., & Blanco, J. Influence of abutment height on maintenance of
512 peri-implant crestal bone at bone-level implants: A 3-year follow-up study. *The International Journal of Periodontics &
513 Restorative Dentistry*, 2017; 37(5),721–727. <https://doi.org/10.11607/prd.2762>.
- 514 56. Schwarz, F., Becker, K., Sahm, N., Horstkemper, T., Rousi, K., Becker J. The prevalence of peri-implant diseases for two-piece
515 implants with an internal tube-in-tube connection: A cross-sectional analysis of 512 implants. *Clinical Oral Implants Research*,
516 2017; 28(1), 24–28. <https://doi.org/10.1111/clar.12609>.
- 517 57. Vervaeke, S., Matthys, C., Nassar, R., Christiaens, V., Cosyn, J., De Bruyn, H. Adapting the vertical position of implants with a
518 conical connection in relation to soft tissue thickness prevents early implant surface exposure: A 2-year prospective intra-subject
519 comparison. *Journal of Clinical Periodontology*, 2018; 45(5), 605–612. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpe.12871>